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TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND JOB SATISFACTION; AN ANALYTIC INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

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The study explored the relationship between transformational leadership of principals and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Muzaffarabad. The study was limited to teachers working in government male and female secondary schools in Muzaffarabad. It was a descriptive correlational study and the survey method was used for data collection. A total sample of 254 secondary school teachers and 90 principals were selected using a convenient sampling technique. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) and the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) were the two tools used to gather the data. Data was collected through personal visits to the schools. Data was analyzed by applying Pearson's correlation. The study found a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. This study indicates that effective transformational leadership can contribute to higher job satisfaction among teachers. Future research could explore additional factors influencing this relationship.

Keywords: transformational leadership, job satisfaction, secondary school teachers, Muzaffarabad, correlational study.

Introduction

In modern organizational perspectives, considering the intricate relationship between transformational leadership styles and employee job satisfaction is fundamental for the development of conducive work situations and successful organizational accomplishment (Akdere, & Tarcan, 2015). Among the several leadership approaches, transformational leadership has garnered significant consideration for its potential to positively affect employee attitudes and behaviours. Regarded for its prominence on inspiration, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence, transformational leadership has the potential to enlighten motivated and involved workers (Pawar, 2016). Job satisfaction, attending as a key display of employee well-being and organizational efficiency, and attitudes as a focal point for exploring the influence of transformational leadership (Jena, Pradhan, & Panigrahy, 2018). Through an inclusive investigation of existing literature and empirical data, this study determined that transformational leadership influences job satisfaction, providing valuable inferences for administrative leaders and investigators.

The teachers would get attracted to teaching their students successfully when they are satisfied with their jobs (Heller, 2004). Like Pakistan, they are trying to improve their quality of education, so that it meets the demand of globalization. Teachers would perform to maximum capacity, only if they are satisfied with their jobs. So, job satisfaction is an important phenomenon in every sector particularly in the teaching profession (Swedana, 2023).

Job satisfaction among teachers is a significant issue since it has an impact on how each performs in his or her position, which has an impact on the effectiveness of their instruction and the operation of the school (Caprara et al., 2003). Teacher job satisfaction is strongly correlated with students' academic

accomplishment; the level of the teacher's job satisfaction can ensure a significant impact on both the teacher's lifecycle and particularly on the student's achievements (Chamundeswari, 2013). Meeting students' educational, psychological, and expressive requirements are directly related to their level of job satisfaction (Lors, 2020).

Consequently, for individual employees to accomplish their jobs as effectively as possible, management leaders must understand what motivates and activates employees. Motivation is linked to performance and job satisfaction (Diab, 2022).

In all management disciplines, leadership is a basic procedure that involves several responsibilities that might assist an organization in achieving its objectives. To this end, experts in leadership and academics offer associations practical recommendations for improving organizational performance (Triraharjo et al., 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The problem under consideration is the potential influence of transformational leadership, established by school principals, on the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Muzaffarabad. Job satisfaction is central to employee well-being and efficiency, predominantly in the education sector, where it affects teacher retention and inclusive job performance (Madigan, & Kim, 2021). High incoming duties and informed dissatisfaction among secondary school teachers' attitude challenges to educational excellence. Although transformational leadership is recognized as effective, its specific effect on teacher job satisfaction in Muzaffarabad remains uncertain. Considerate this relationship is dynamic for apprising leadership practices and policies to develop teacher satisfaction and student learning experiences. Existing investigation has focused on leadership styles generally, but there's a lack of consideration for transformational leadership's influence on teacher satisfaction

in Muzaffarabad, requiring a dedicated exploration. This study aims to assist school principals, policymakers, researchers, and educators in the search to develop leadership practices and teacher satisfaction in Muzaffarabad's secondary schools.

Significance of the Research

The significance of the research on transformational leadership and job satisfaction is to notify leadership practices and policies in educational situations. By exploring the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers, this study can provide an appreciated understanding for school administrators, policymakers, and instructors. Accepting how transformational leadership encourages job satisfaction can be central to the development of additional effective leadership training programs and approaches for school principals. Additionally, by successful job satisfaction among teachers, schools can increase employee retention rates, eventually prominent to better educational consequences for learners. This exploration also contributes to the existing body of knowledge on leadership styles and their influence on employee well-being, mostly from the perspective of secondary education in Muzaffarabad. Generally, the results of this study have the prospect of positively affecting the work situation and overall efficiency of secondary schools in Muzaffarabad and elsewhere.

Objective of the Study

The objective is to assess the correlation between transformational leadership exhibited by principals and the job satisfaction levels of secondary school teachers in Muzaffarabad. The study aims to determine whether there is a significant positive relationship between these variables. Precisely, it searches to determine whether effective transformational leadership among

principals correlates with higher levels of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses of the Study

The study employed the following hypothesis:

H₁: Transformational leadership has a positive relationship with job satisfaction.

Literature Review

Transformational leadership and job satisfaction are two fundamental factors that significantly impact organizational efficiency and employee well-being (Nielsen et al., 2009). Bass & Riggio (2006) state transformational leadership as an activity where individuals forge relationships that increase both followers' and leaders' levels of work-related interest. Syed, Channa, & Khoso (2020) examine the strong connection between job satisfaction and employees' willingness to work, accentuating its significant effect on motivation.

Many studies have explored the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers such as Dewi, Yulianto, and Ruswanti (2022) explore the significant positive correlation between transformational leadership shown by head teachers and teachers' job satisfaction, signifying the potential of effective leadership in enhancing teacher satisfaction. Consistently, Firmansyah et al., (2022) highlighted the significant effect of transformational leadership on teachers' job satisfaction within the classroom.

Moreover, an investigation by Rao, (2023) highlights the influence of administrators' role showing on teachers' self-efficacy, specifying the significance of leadership behaviour in influencing teacher attitudes. Chaudhuri, & Ghosh, (2012) concentrated on the critical role of social assignment in encouraging positive change concluding transformational leadership within organizations.

In addition, Dalton, (2023) determines how truthful and faithful followers contribute to

the effectiveness of transformational leadership, prominent to improved motivation and possession of organizational goals. [Givens \(2008\)](#) accentuated the positive correlation between inspiration and enthusiasm to work with followers' views of their superiors, emphasizing the motivational effect of transformational leadership.

As well, the literature recommends a mutual relationship between leaders' commitment and followers' satisfaction ([Huo et al., 2020](#)). [Metwally, El-Bishbishy, & Nawar, \(2014\)](#) establish a direct correlation between transformational leadership and employee satisfaction, representing the role of transformative leaders in addressing employees' anxieties. Likewise, studies have accentuated the vital role of transformational leadership in motivating teacher effectiveness and curriculum implementation ([Sirait, 2021](#)). [Shatila, Agyei, & Aloulou, \(2023\)](#) emphasize the direct link between performance and transformational leadership, highlighting the motivational influence of transformative leaders.

Transformational leadership and job satisfaction are two important factors that influence organizational effectiveness and employee well-being. [Stewart, \(2012\)](#) expresses transformational leadership as an action where individuals falsify relationships that boost both followers' and leaders' levels of work-related eagerness. [Zahari et al., \(2020\)](#) explored the strong association between job satisfaction and employees' inclination to effort, emphasizing its generous influence on inspiration.

Although the wealth of exploration associates the positive relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, there is a necessity for more investigation, particularly in non-Western circumstances like Muzaffarabad. More controlled studies are needed to recognize the dynamics of this relationship completely and its implications for educational consequences.

Conceptual Framework

Explanation of the Components:

1. **Transformational Leadership:** This is the independent variable in the study. It represents the leadership style of school teachers that involves inspiring, motivating, and empowering teachers to achieve their best.
2. **Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers:** This is the dependent variable in the study. It represents the level of contentment, fulfilment, and positive feelings experienced by secondary school teachers in Muzaffarabad regarding their jobs.
3. **Relationship Exploration:** This component signifies the main focus of the study, which is to explore the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.
4. **Contextual Factors:** These are external factors that could influence the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. Contextual factors might include cultural norms, organizational climate, school policies, and regional socio-economic conditions. This conceptual framework visualizes the central components of the study and the relationships among them.

Visual Representation Fig 1

Research Methodology

The quantitative research methodology was employed to investigate the relationship between transformational leadership on the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Muzaffarabad. To achieve the research objectives, a quantitative research design was adopted, utilizing a survey questionnaire. This approach enabled the collection of data from a considerable sample of secondary school teachers, facilitating the exploration of the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. The target group was comprised of both male and female secondary school teachers and principals in Muzaffarabad. A convenient sampling technique was employed total sample size of 254 teachers and 90 principals, ensuring appropriate representation and minimizing sampling errors.

The research instruments comprise the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) adopted and the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), developed by [Spector \(1994\)](#) used originally after getting permission. These standardized tools have been widely recognized and validated for assessing transformational leadership and job satisfaction, respectively. The MLQ measures leadership styles, specifically focusing on the transformational leadership dimension, while the JSS evaluates job satisfaction. The instruments were carefully adapted to fit the regional context translated into Urdu and validated through expert consultation, ensuring their relevance to the study. Ethical considerations were strictly followed throughout the data collection process, with participants' informed consent and confidentiality being maintained.

The data analysis process incorporated inferential statistics, utilizing software like SPSS version 21. Inferential statistics, such as Pearson's correlation coefficient, were employed to make inferences about the larger population and explore relationships between variables.

Results and Discussion

Pearson Correlation, Relationship between Transformational Leadership of Principals and Job Satisfaction of the Secondary School Teachers

H2: Transformational leadership has a positive relationship with job satisfaction.

Correlations

		Job Satisfaction	Transformational Leadership
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.216
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	254	254
Transformational Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.216	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	254	254

The table presents the Pearson correlation between the transformational leadership of principals and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables, the two variables being examined are job satisfaction and transformational leadership. This indicates a positive correlation between the two variables. It suggests that there is a moderate positive relationship between the level of transformational leadership exhibited by principals and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

The significance (Sig.) value of 0.001 is highly statistically significant. This means that the observed correlation is unlikely to occur by chance and is likely a true relationship between the variables. Therefore, we can conclude that there is a significant positive correlation between transformational leadership and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Both variables have the same correlation coefficient and significance value, indicating a

symmetrical relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. This means that higher levels of transformational leadership are associated with higher levels of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers, and vice versa. The sample size (N) of 254 participants provides a relatively large dataset, which increases the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

We would accept the H_1 and conclude that Transformational leadership has a positive relationship with job satisfaction. The table shows that there is a significant positive correlation between the transformational leadership of principals and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. This suggests that when principals exhibit higher levels of transformational leadership, it tends to result in increased job satisfaction among teachers.

The results are consistent with previous research that has demonstrated that transformational leadership practices positively affect employee attitudes and well-being (Cassar, Bezzina, & Buttigieg, 2017). When school principals exhibit transformational leadership behaviours, teachers are more likely to feel valued, motivated, and engaged, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction.

The results obtained from the analysis of the correlation between transformational leadership and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers are consistent with existing literature in the field of organizational psychology and educational leadership. Firstly, the positive correlation coefficient of 0.216 between transformational leadership and job satisfaction aligns with previous research findings. Murphy, & Anderson, (2020) conducted a study that established the positive impact of transformational leadership on employee attitudes and well-being. This suggests that when principals exhibit higher levels of transformational leadership behaviours, such as inspiring and motivating

their staff, it leads to increased job satisfaction among teachers.

Moreover, the significance level (Sig.) of 0.001 indicates a highly statistically significant relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. This repeats the findings of previous studies, such as Stewart (2006), who highlighted the perspective of transformational leadership to inspire and enable followers to exceed their prospects. Adillo, & Netshitangani, (2019) also emphasized the crucial role of transformational principals in the development of a positive school environment, where teachers feel appreciated, motivated, and engaged in their work.

Also, the symmetrical relationship observed between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, with both variables involving the same correlation coefficient and significance value, emphasizes the concept that higher levels of transformational leadership are associated with higher levels of job satisfaction among teachers, and vice versa (Abdul et al., 2014).

Mehari, (2015) suggested that transformational leaders show genuine anxiety for their followers' well-being and professional progress, which in turn improves job satisfaction. The correlation analysis showed in this study, examining the relationship between the transformational leadership of principals and the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers, aligns with the preceding study findings. The positive correlation coefficient of 0.216 recommends a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. This aligns with studies like those by Balogun, & Tella, (2022) which establish parallel positive relationships between transformational leadership and job satisfaction in different administrative circumstances.

The highly significant p-value of 0.001 in the correlation investigation highlights the

strength of the perceived relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, confirming its statistical significance. This finding resonates with the scholarly work of Braun, Peus, Weisweiler, & Frey, (2013), who accentuated the critical role of statistically significant relationships in demonstrating the credibility of associations between leadership styles and employee job satisfaction. In addition, the considerable sample size of 254 participants increases the reliability and generalizability of the study's conclusions, aligning with recognized best practices supported by Carte, & Russell, (2003).

Notably, the seminal work of Bass, & Bass, (2009) is viewed as a significant illustration of this phenomenon. Their inclusive research delved into diverse organizational contexts and effectively revealed a purposeful positive correlation between transformational leadership behaviours and employee job satisfaction levels.

Additionally, a wider perspective on this topic is provided by the understanding meta-analysis conducted by Judge, Piccolo, & Ilies, (2004) Concluded a comprehensive synthesis of numerous studies, their findings significant relationship between transformational leadership and the enhancement of job satisfaction across various organizational situations.

The findings of this research support and extend upon the conclusions drawn by Wang, & Howell, (2012) through rigorous data analysis, the study confirmed a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between transformational leadership and job satisfaction.

Conclusion

The findings of this study expose a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership of principals and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. The Pearson correlation coefficient analysis indicates a strong correlation ($r =$

$0.216, p < 0.001$) between these two variables, providing empirical support for the hypothesis, which suggested a positive relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. These results highlight the importance of transformational leadership in impelling the job satisfaction levels of teachers within secondary school situations. Transformational leaders concluded their capability to inspire, motivate, and intellectually stimulate their subordinates, and contribute to a positive work environment that promotes satisfaction among teachers. This satisfaction, in turn, has implications for various aspects of educational practices, including teaching effectiveness, staff retention, and eventually, student consequences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, some recommendations developed for educational leaders, policymakers, and researchers:

Leadership Development Programs: Educational leaders should participate in leadership development programs that focus on promotion and attractive transformational leadership skills among principals and other school managers. These platforms should accentuate the importance of encouraging a compassionate and inspiring work environment that arranges the well-being and satisfaction of teachers.

Supportive Work Environments: School administrators should enthusiastically encourage supportive work environments where teachers feel valued, respected, and empowered. This may encourage open communication, provide occasions for professional growth and progress, and identify the aid of teachers to the school community.

Continuing Evaluation and Feedback: Regular evaluation and feedback mechanisms should be executed to consider the leadership practices of principals and their influence on teacher job satisfaction. This feedback can appraise targeted interferences and

modifications to leadership attitudes to better meet the needs and opportunities of teachers.

Future Research Directions: Further research is justified to explore the essential mechanisms concluded in which transformational leadership influences job satisfaction among teachers. Longitudinal studies can arrange for an understanding of the long-term effects of transformational leadership on teacher satisfaction and preservation. As well, qualitative research methods can offer a deeper appreciation of the subjective experiences and observations of teachers concerning their relations with transformational leaders.

The positive relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction identified in this study highlights the importance of effective leadership practices in promoting a conducive work setting within secondary schools. By placing in order the development of transformational leadership skills and promotion of supportive work environments, educational leaders can enhance teacher satisfaction and, eventually, add to better educational consequences for students.

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Annexure A

Paul Spector <paul@paulspector.com>

To me

Dear Inaam:

You have my permission to use the original JSS in your research. You can find copies of the scale in the original English and several other languages, as well as details about the scale's development and norms, in the [Paul's No Cost Assessments](#) section of my website: <https://paulspector.com>. I allow free use for noncommercial research and teaching purposes in return for the sharing of results. This includes student theses and dissertations, as well as other student research projects. Copies of the scale can be reproduced in a thesis or dissertation as long as the copyright notice is included, "Copyright Paul E. Spector 1994, All rights reserved." Results can be shared by providing an e-copy of a published or unpublished research report (e.g., a dissertation). You also have permission to translate the JSS into another language under the same conditions in addition to sharing a copy of the translation with me. Be sure to include the copyright statement, as well as credit the person who did the translation with the year.

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For additional assessment resources including an archive of measures developed by others, check out the assessment section of my website for organizational measures <https://paulspector.com/assessments/> and my companion site for general and mental health measures: <https://www.stevenericspector.com/mental-health-assessment-archive/>

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